

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Analysis of the pedigrees of japonica rice varieties released in Taiwan

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We studied changes in the genetic diversity of japonica rice varieties released in Taiwan over five time periods: 1940-49, 1950-59, 1960-69, 1970-79, and 1980-89. Relative genetic contributions were computed to quantify the genetic constituents of 99 varieties into theoretical percentages attributable to different ancestors.

The varieties were traced back to 65 ancestors, 44 of them Japanese plant introductions. Only 11 were from Taiwan. Japanese introductions contributed more than 85% of the genes. Although more ancestors were integrated into later breeding programs, as few as

Relative genetic contributions and occurrence of the 10 most important ancestral contributors to 99 varieties released in Taiwan 1940-89.

Ancestor	Mean genetic contribution	Cumulative genetic contribution	Occurrence (no.) in pedigrees
Hodoyoshi	0.213	0.213	83
Kameji	0.167	0.380	80
NC 4	0.065	0.445	45
Oloan-chu	0.061	0.506	43
Iyosengoku	0.037	0.543	26
Aikoku	0.037	0.580	46
Osaka Asahi	0.023	0.603	19
Iwata Asahi	0.020	0.623	23
Kairio Aikoku	0.019	0.642	20
Yoshino I	0.018	0.660	9

10 contributors comprised more than 70% of the genetic constituents of the released varieties in each time period.

Two Japanese introductions predominated in mean relative genetic contributions of genes: Hodoyoshi with 21.3% and Kameji with 16.7% (see table). At least 83 of the 99 varieties released in the last 50 yr (including all 11 varieties released in 1980-87) are more or less related because of the Hodoyoshi link.

This shows the narrow genetic base in current japonica rice varieties. Extensive use of superior varieties such as Taichung 65 is the major reason integration of diverse plant introductions did not result in diversification of released germplasm. Crosses to elite genotypes that carry specific gene complexes conditioning desirable traits should be made with caution, to avoid decreasing the genetic diversity among released varieties. ■

Widely compatible japonica rice from Yunnan, China

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Yunnan local rice variety Haomei carries resistance to nine strains of bacterial blight (*Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*): Jiangling 691, OS75, 76-27, and KS-6-6 from China and PXO61, PXO86, PXO79, PXO71, and PXO211 from the Philippines. It is susceptible to strain PXO99 from the Philippines.

Resistance of Haomei to Chinese strain Jiangling 691 is governed by a newly identified dominant gene, tentatively designated as *Xa-i*. *Xa-i* is linked to the marker gene *nl-1* (neck leaf-1) located on linkage group 5. The recom-

bination value between *Xa-i* and *nl-1* is $37.3 \pm 3.9\%$ by maximum likelihood estimation.

Haomei is a widely compatible japonica. Fertility with indica testers is $73.72 \pm 4.63\%$; that with japonica testers is $77.13 \pm 11.08\%$.

Haomei has glabrous leaf and hull and glutinous endosperm. The hull is covered

with purple blots, with fewer over the glume bulge. Rice base-solubility (1.7% KOH treatment for 23 h under 30 °C) belongs to grade 4.

It is medium-tillering with large panicles averaging 239 grains. Grain weight is 35.2 g per 1000. Plant height is about 120 cm in Wuchang, Hubei Province. ■

Genetics

Heritability of seedling vigor characters

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Poor seedling emergence associated with seedling vigor characters is a major constraint to the adoption of direct seeding for irrigated and rainfed lowland rice. Heritability is the fraction of variation in a trait that is attributable to

genetic causes. It is a property not only of a character, but also of the plant population and the environmental circumstances of the crop.

We used variance partitioning of segregating populations (VPSP) and offspring:parent ($F_3:F_2$) regression and correlation in four crosses to estimate narrow sense heritability (H_n) for mesocotyl, coleoptile, and seedling length.

H_n for mesocotyl length was comparatively higher than for coleoptile and seedling length (see table). The